

CONTEMPORARY THEATRICAL ART IN THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER

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Abstract

The article discusses the features of theatrical pedagogy in the process of educating children of different ages. The interest of the pedagogical community is manifested in social and theatrical practices, which can become one of the ways to return theater pedagogy to the modern educational process.

Keywords: art, modern theatrical art, pedagogical creativity, theatrical pedagogy, educational activities.

Modern theatrical art is considered in two aspects in the article: as a way of solving the problems of educating students and as a means of preparing future teachers to solve educational tasks (theater pedagogy). At the same time, educational activity is understood in terms of the position of a culturological approach as a purposeful activity of a teacher acting as an intermediary between a child and culture to involve students in the context of modern culture.

Undoubtedly theatrical art has a high educational potential and is favorable for the effective informal implementation of educational tasks. In the system of additional education of artistic orientation, the activities of theatrical creative associations have a rich history. The educational process of the theater collective has always been aimed at introducing children to the best traditions of literature and art, the best examples of theatrical culture, at fostering a moral attitude, at educating the child's personality.

A considerable number of scientific works in the field of pedagogy and psychology are devoted to the problems of upbringing and education by means of theater. The effectiveness of the use of theatrical pedagogy in the process of teaching and educating children of different ages, including adolescents, is proved in the works of V. M. Bukatov, N. S. Vladimirova, A. P. Ershova, A. B. Nikitina, E. K. Chukhman, A. V. Grebenkin, O. S. Zadorina, etc. The studies of O. N. Antonova, I. J. Generalova, T. G. Penya, as much as Ya. Mikhailova, L. M. Nekrasova, M. P. Stul and others are devoted to the education of general culture by means of the theater.

Teachers should introduce mandatory interaction with art into the life of the child, not as a separate and rare event, but as a permanent and mandatory element of education. Interaction with art, the author continues, is not a simple informational accumulation of knowledge. Art is always the communication of a person with people through an artistic image, it is necessary to figure out together with children what it is: what does it tell us? what is amazing? what worries you? Why did the artist take a pen, a brush? And most importantly: how life is reflected in this work [9, p. 59].

It should be clarified that "school theater pedagogy", being a part of theater pedagogy, has its own goals that differ from the goals of theater pedagogy. If the goal of theater pedagogy is the professional training of actors and directors, then by "theatrical work with

children", or "school theater pedagogy", we mean "education of the student's personality by means of theatrical art". The main goal of school theater pedagogy is "the development of imagination and imaginative thinking of the student", his/her attitude to life, to himself/herself, to another person, and hence the development of his personality [2, p. 37].

In a modern school, traditional forms of theatrical work with a younger generation are becoming less and less demanding. School theaters and drama clubs are a thing of the past as archaic forms of extracurricular educational work. There are several reasons for this situation: the virtualization of society, the strengthening of the influence of information and communication technologies. A modern teenager is under the influence of social networks and computer games, he no longer wants to be just a passive observer and contemplator, he wants to influence the course of events.

One of the reasons for the decline in the pedagogic and educational influence of the theater on schoolchildren is the unwillingness and inability of professional teams to work with teenagers in new socio-cultural conditions, when interest in traditional forms of art which can also include theaters. In most professional theaters for children and youth, there is no teacher in the staff schedule who could take the organization of interactive theater practices that are so in demand in adolescence. But most importantly, the professional theater community needs to learn how to talk to children and teenagers honestly and not be afraid to raise modern problems.

The involvement of the viewer and participant in the creative process, where the performance (or any other theatrical form) is born here and now, where improvisation and unpredictability are fully an integral part of the performance, can become one of the ways to return theatrical pedagogy to the modern educational process. The possibility of using theatrical pedagogical technologies in working with teenagers, which contribute to the formation of stage improvisational skills, will undoubtedly contribute to their successful socialization [4, p.6].

It is known that factors such as genetics, social environment, culture and individual experience influence the development of personality. Self-determination, according to S. L. Rubinstein (a soviet psychologist and philosopher), is "the search by a subject for his way of life in the world on the basis of perceived, accepted or formed by him in a time perspective basic relations to the world, other people, the human community as a

whole and to himself, as well as on the basis of his own system of life meanings and principles, values and ideals, opportunities and abilities, expectations and claims."

The period of emergence of the conscious "I" is adolescents and young people, therefore it is necessary to take into account that inclusion in various communities (fitting different social roles) contributes to building a set of values and guidelines, and at the same time understanding life issues, prudence and motivation necessary for successful personal development.

It is possible to directly influence the motivational, emotional-imaginative and intellectual-creative sides of the personality of students using the means of this pedagogy. In theatrical art, there is no contrast between the emotional-figurative and the intellectual-logical [6, p.109].

Modern theatrical art has a number of features that make it in demand both in the process of preparing future teachers for educational activities and in solving educational tasks at school. Among such features, the most significant in the context of education are the following:

- the brightness and originality of the works of modern theatrical art attract the attention of both students and schoolchildren. The catchy, unusual external form stimulates interest in the inner content of the works, makes you think about the spiritual, moral, social problem underlying the theatrical action, creates an emotional mood necessary for its serious and thoughtful discussion;

- minimalism, characteristic of many modern performances, allows you to focus not on the aesthetics of the design of the performance, but on the essence of the underlying conflict, which is especially important when solving problems of spiritual and moral education;

- a large selection of genres and trends in the field of modern theatrical art (solo performances, musicals, documentary theater, performance and much more) allows you to take into account the individual capabilities of students when choosing a performance for viewing, discussion or staging by students;

- the interactive nature of modern theatrical art, which allows schoolchildren to formulate, justify and defend their own moral position, and future teachers to "play" various situations of professional activity in the field of education, develop their creative abilities, the ability to interact with strangers in non-standard conditions in the mode of improvisation. Many modern theatrical productions belong to the so-called immersive art. Such performances contain elements of a quest, a musical, and include computer game plots. The audience are active participants and co-creators of the action, can choose one of several storylines;

- a special organization of the space of the modern theater, which allows the audience not only to actively participate in the theatrical action, but also to hear the actors' replicas better, see the details of their costumes, gestures, facial expressions and as a result – to understand their feelings and experiences more deeply.

Of course, there are also elements in modern theatrical art, the use of which is unacceptable when solving educational tasks. Violation of moral taboos, the use of obscene vocabulary, anti-value content – all this is the basis for excluding the work from the context of education.

Thus, students develop the ability to feel empathy, to an adequate external expression of emotions; a combination of artistic and creative activities and computer technologies in modern theatrical productions, adequate to the worldview of representatives of the younger generation and allowing them to better understand the basic idea of the performance.

Modern domestic and foreign researchers consider theatricalization as a phenomenon of modern life, as part of modern reality. This approach seems to be very promising from the point of view of the principle of the connection of education with life [3, p.60].

Theatrical experience in educational organizations successfully helps students in this cognitive process. Firstly, the theatrical form (like any "game") tends to interest and involve a large number of students in the process. Secondly, this form implies the need for communication, the disclosure of creative (and, accordingly, personal) potential, and also develops the independent thinking and understanding of the problems posed in the performance necessary for self-determination. Taking the role of another person in theatrical activity, acting on his behalf, a teenager learns both himself and the "other", which ultimately contributes to the development of his self-consciousness [5, p.46].

Thus, it can be concluded that modern forms of theatrical art (social theater, forum theater, etc.) can bring theater back into pedagogical practice as an effective method of teaching and upbringing. Theater pedagogy educates a teenager and prepares him for life in a modern society that imposes certain requirements. New theatrical and social forms of work with the younger generation require teachers to rethink the goals and objectives of pedagogical activity, the main of which is the formation of social activity in the subject of the pedagogical process. It is necessary to provide freedom of choice and teach to make decisions about certain actions on the basis of moral consciousness. The ultimate goal of education is the formed active life and creative position of the student, which is expressed in the development of the basic values of modern russian society.

From the point of view of the organization of educational activities, such features of modern theatrical art as originality, the predominance of ideological content over external design, interactive nature, strengthening of "virtuality" through the use of computer technology are significant.

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